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LAND USE LAND COVER CHANGE IMPACT ON WATER RESOURCES - A REVIEW

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Abstract:

The land use change has generally occurred locally, regionally and worldwide over the last few decades and will carry on in the future as well. The increment in urbanization has a major impact on groundwater and it is major concern over the few years to those who are involved in groundwater studies. The enlargement of the urbanization area results in decrease in infiltration, which affect the groundwater recharge and storage. The land use change has to be evaluated properly using conventional as well as latest techniques of Remote Sensing and Geographical Information System (GIS). The overpopulation often leads to increase in food and fuel demands with quick change in land use pattern. From the era when the human evolution started, mankind's trust on environment is greater, surplus hunt of progress, comfort and security has resulted in increased stress on the environment. Proper planning and management for development of natural resources without threatening the environment is a crucial concern to be sorted out for the world population. Rigorous efforts on the rate and pattern of land use change are indispensable for suitable implementation and execution. Land use change pattern reveals the rate of change of groundwater recharge. It is necessary to identify the land use change in the past and present accessible land use, and its allocated and potential changes are major rudiments for planning and management. The success for proper socio-economic upliftment of a region and country is proper land use planning and management.

Keywords: GIS, Remote Sensing, Land use, groundwater

Introduction:

Water is essential for sustaining life on earth. The demand of water is increasing year to year with the ever rising population. For masses population water is the basic requirement for drinking and food production. For agriculture sector the supply of water for irrigation requires much more effort as the source of water is limited and

non uniform distribution pattern of water with respect to space and time (cgwb.gov.in). Depending on single sources for any purpose is much unreliable and the idea of using water for two or more alternative sources with economic condition is drawing the attention of planners, engineers, and decision makers. The prospects of practicing conjunctive use of surface and groundwater will be better, provided one understands the hydrological balance cycle the various hydrological components are estimated on a seasonal basis for monsoon, Pre-monsoon and Post-monsoon seasons. Fresh water is the livelihood of the planet. No one can survive without it. The ultimate source of fresh water is rain and snow. Fresh water systems are the rivers, streams, lakes, groundwater, cave water, glaciers and wet lands.

Demand for groundwater is increasing while the water resources remain almost constant. Therefore, continuous withdrawals of groundwater may result in depletion of water table. It is necessary to maintain the water level fluctuations have to be kept within a particular range over the monsoon and non-monsoon seasons (www.sys.virginia.edu). In spite of the favorable average availability of groundwater, there are some areas in the country having scarcity of water. From time immemorial, in last few decades the significance of groundwater has increased as it is one of the major source of water for the food production in India. (Dhirendra Kumar Singh,2002).

The precipitated water is subjected to various processes such as interception, evaporation, and surface runoff out of which, some of the infiltrate into the soil which is used by plants and remaining water continue percolate deeper into the soil column which contributes to groundwater recharge (Mikko L Jyrkama 2007). Groundwater is intimately connected with the landscape and is vulnerable to the anthropogenic activities on the land surface. Land use effects of groundwater resources through changes in recharge and by changing demands for water (David N. Lerner 2009).

Water is a sensitive issue for the existence of all living organisms. Only few use salt water like coral reefs, mammals like blue whale, jelly fish etc but majority of living organisms must have access to fresh water to live. Few terrestrial mammals, especially desert rodents survive without drinking but they do procreate water through the metabolism of cereal seeds and they also have adaptable features which helps them to conserve water to the maximum degree. Saline water in oceans, seas and saline groundwater make up about 96.5% of it. 2.5–2.75% is fresh water, including 1.75–2% frozen state in glaciers, ice and snow 0.5–0.75% as fresh groundwater and soil moisture, and less than 0.01% of it as surface water in lakes, swamps and rivers.

Recent activities carried or done in the name of human development has affected the quantity and quality of groundwater. The increase in the industrialization and rapid population growth has resulted in rapid increase in land-use change phenomena in many areas (J. Dams, 2008). Management strategies on the development of groundwater resource while the growing demand for water by communities and industries. For example Urban/Land use, Cropping Pattern, Industrialization etc. The demand of water is increased; this demand is met with groundwater.

The impact of urbanization implicates in groundwater quantity and qualitative studies. Increased in urbanization, decreases infiltration. Land use planning and management approaches are key for development. It has been reported that in many parts of the country the water table is declining at the rate of 1-2m/year (thirdworldcentre.org).

Literature Review:

Groundwater is the water held underground in the soil or in pores and crevices in rock. A body of permeable rock which can contain or transmit groundwater is called an aquifer when it can yield a usable quantity of water. The depth at which soil pore spaces or fractures and voids in rock are unable to hold or contain any more amount of water is called the water table. Groundwater is recharged from seeping of rain water from pores of the upper soil layer which ultimately flows to the surface naturally. The naturally occurring discharge often collects

at springs and seeps, which eventually forms oases or wetlands. Groundwater is also used for the purpose of irrigation, civic, and industrial use by constructing and operating extraction wells.

Twenty one percent of the world's fresh water is groundwater, which is about 0.61% of the entire world's water. The total amount of freshwater stored in the snow and ice pack, including the north and south poles is roughly equal to worldwide groundwater storage. This makes it significant resource that can be used as a natural storage that can buffer against shortages of surface water, as in during times of drought.

Human activities have exerted small to large scale changes on the hydrological cycle. The current scenario regarding groundwater resources suggests that globally there is a water crisis in terms of quantity (availability) and quality. Therefore there is a great need for the assessment and monitoring of quality and quantity of groundwater resources at local level. Land use changes are altering the hydrologic system and have potentially large impacts on water resources. The increase in population and the rapid socio-economic development drives land use change. (K. Schneider 2013).it is the one of the most vibrant research topic in the field of hydrology. (Wang genxu, 2005)

The evaluation of land use changes has to be done by both traditional and latest techniques such as Remote Sensing and Geographical Information System (GIS).

Land use change impact on groundwater

Over the last few decades a major concern is the impact of urbanization on groundwater, and in particular, to those involved in groundwater quantity and qualitative studies. Urbanization results in increased in impervious area due to decreased infiltration, and finally affecting the groundwater storage. Due to increase of settlement area will directly impact the decrease of ground water level. The social and economic development of a region lies in proper land use planning and groundwater management of the region. Over population has resulted in increase in demand which eventually has lead to accelerated rate of urbanization which results in reduction in infiltration, and thus affecting the groundwater recharge and storage.

Assessment of Annual replenishable groundwater resources using water level fluctuation approach and empirical norms, estimation of the annual quantity of groundwater withdrawal and categorization of the assessment units based on the status of groundwater utilization and water level trend are the methodology adopted for groundwater observation.

Impact on groundwater recharge

As there is increase in usage of groundwater a major concern is also the decrease in rate of recharge of groundwater. The rate of recharge is decreasing exponentially with time.

Earth's largest freshwater resource is Groundwater. Reduced reliability of surface water supplies in the western US with projected climate change during the next century may result in increased reliance on groundwater. Widespread changes in LU/LC have occurred as a result of agricultural expansion. In the past 300 years, cultivated cropland has increased by factors of 70 in the US and 5 globally (Richards, 1990).It is important to understand how land use change impacts groundwater recharge, especially for regions that are undergoing rapid urbanization and there is limited surface water. In this study, the hydrological processes and recharge ability of various land use

types in Guishui River Basin, China (in Beijing Municipality) were analyzed. The results indicate that groundwater recharge accounts for only 21.16% of the precipitation, while 72.54% is lost in the form of evapotranspiration. The annual-lumped groundwater recharge rate decreases in the order of cropland, grassland, urban land, and forest. Land use change has resulted in a decrease of $4 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ of yearly groundwater recharge in the study area, with a spatially averaged rate of 100.48 mm/yr and 98.41 mm/yr in 1980 and 2005, respectively. This variation has primarily come from an increase of urban area and rural settlements, as well as a decrease of cropland. (Nakagoshi 2011).

Another problem with groundwater is the contamination of the water. Being a renewable source groundwater has to be protected from contamination. Many developing countries have adopted the concept of a zone of protection for areas containing. In India one such area is Tirupur, (Tamil Nadu, India), an arid region and rapid expansion of the textile industry has taken. Textile production, particularly dyeing and bleaching is water intensive and generates large quantities of effluent. One of the most significant challenges for the Tirupur textile industry today is water for bleaching and disposal of effluent (Teloglou, 2008).

A practice such as intensive irrigation in major canal commands which results in overexploitation of groundwater has posed serious problems for groundwater managers in India. Recent researches have showed that the water table is declining at the rate of 1–2 m/year (Singh 2010) in many parts of the country. If these problems are overlooked then the day where there is problem of water scarcity is not far.

The water table fall as a result of decreased soil infiltration, e.g. through non-conservation farming techniques and compaction (Tejwani, 1993). Also, heavy grazing may lead to reduced infiltration and groundwater recharge (Chomitz and Kumari, 1996). If the infiltration capacity is substantially reduced, this can lead to water shortages in dry seasons, even in regions where water is usually abundant, like in the case of shifting cultivation in Cherapunji province, India (FAO, 1999). Groundwater recharge can be reduced as a result of planting of deep rooting tree species, e.g. eucalyptus (Calder, 1998).

Groundwater recharge is also affected by land use and land cover in semi-arid or arid areas. Variations in recharge associated with LU/LC changes can have negative impacts on groundwater quality because thick unsaturated zones in semiarid and arid regions contain a reservoir of salts that accumulated over thousands of years (Allison et al., 1990; Phillips, 2003; Walvoord et al., 2003) and can be flushed into underlying aquifers.

China have been selected for study, resulting in that groundwater recharge beneath natural sparse small grass was 100 mm/year, but the conversion to winter wheat about 100 years ago has reduced groundwater recharge to 55 mm/year. (Tianming, 2010). In arid and semi-arid areas, groundwater resource is a sensitive factor of ecological environment and helps to maintain vegetation in naturally occurring desert oases, as well as the social stability and economy in this desert environment. An accurate understanding of the spatiotemporal variability of groundwater is very for making reasonable plans of oasis development and ensuring ecosystem sustainability (Wang, 2015)

It is important to know how land use change influences the groundwater discharge especially for regions that are undergoing rapid imperviousness. In this study, the hydrological process and recharge availability of various land use types in guishui river basin, china were studied. it was found that groundwater recharge predicts decreases in order of cropland, grassland, urban land and forest respectively.(Yun, 2011)

The impact of urbanization implicates in groundwater quantity and qualitative studies. Increased in urbanization decreases infiltration.. It has been reported that in many parts of the country the water table is declining at the rate of 1–2 m/year (thirdworldcentre.org). The quantity and quality of groundwater are changing due to human activity. Since the era of industrialization and rapid population growth, land-use change phenomena have strongly accelerated in many regions which directly impacting the hydrology of the catchment area (J. Dams, 2008)

The effects of land use change on hydrology leads at present to the results that carry quite a bit of uncertainty. Obvious effects are that a forest cover will increase the evapotranspiration, and that urbanization will reduce evapotranspiration and infiltration and increase surface runoff.

Impact on groundwater storage

The current land use change is record over the last 150 years which has major impact on water cycle patterns. Much of this land has changed to agricultural that caused a large loss of wetlands and forests. In the last decades few agricultural lands have been shifted to urban uses because of urban sprawl. The land use impacts show the poor water quality.

The rapid increment in impervious area has resulted in decrease in infiltration of ground water. The exhaustion of ground water storage due to above mentioned fact and also extraction of more groundwater to fulfill the demand. Afforestation in the study area has resulted in higher infiltration to the aquifer in many locations within the study area. The study witnessed increased social and economic condition of the people of the study area due to the irrigation system which promises round the year cultivation. Indira Sagar Canal Command has enhanced the food production in the district and state as a whole. (Prabhakar, 2015)

An important element of the water cycle that describes the loss of water from the groundwater compartment to surface waters is Base flow discharge. Groundwater discharge is influenced by climate, watershed, and land use/management conditions. Forests are an important component in the stabilization of groundwater discharge and stream flow. The Pipiripau river basin, a 235 km² catchment in central Brazil, has experienced a substantial increase in land use intensity (mostly agriculture and pastureland) in the last 40 years. This has contributed to a significant decrease in the base flow discharge, responsible for the maintenance of the stream flow during the dry winter season. To assess the hydrological and economic benefits of three land conservation programs in the basin, an empirical relationship was obtained between the base flow index and the normalized basin curve - number, calibrated with observed stream flow and precipitation data. The results indicate that if reforestation and best management practices are implemented in the basin, up to 755 x 106 m³/a of additional base flow discharge would result during the dry season, with additional revenues up to US\$ 1.03 million per year for the water utility company (Henrique et al., 2011)

To clarify the relationship between landuse changes, the decreases in groundwater table, land use changes. The results shown, the area of bare sandy land in the study region sharply decreased. Agricultural land and forests were the two major ones for water consumptions respectively. (Zheng. X. 2012)

Impact on groundwater quality

Freshwater is a valuable natural resource whose quantity and quality is essential for sustainable development [Vörösmarty 2005]. The quality of water has recently become as important as its quantity because water quality directly affects human and ecological health and the use of water resources Groundwater age, and its influence on contemporary water chemistry, needs to be accurately described to quantify the temporally varying impacts of land use on water quality. The time lags between solute inputs at the land surface and impacts on stream chemistry can be an important factor for managing land use in regional watersheds. The analysis reveals a rapid

deterioration of groundwater quality related mainly to the increase in built-up land with unsewered sanitation and poultry farms. Seasonal variability of the groundwater quality was also assessed. (Ahmed. 2010)

Sewage disposal plant contributes the most in contamination of groundwater in the areas where septic systems are packed as in subdivided tracts in suburban areas and in areas where the bedrock is covered by insignificant amount of soil. Fecal bacteria, including *Coliform* and *Escherichia coli*, are the ones which mostly contaminate groundwater and these are also used as a biomonitoring tool for drinking water quality. The gastrointestinal tract of humans and other warm-blooded animals is the home of fecal coliform bacteria. The traces of these bacteria in groundwater indicates the degradation by human or animal night soil and may be related to septic tank waste.

Water quality assessment involves evaluation of the physical, chemical, and biological nature of water in relation to natural quality, human effects, and intended uses, particularly uses which may affect human health and the health of the aquatic system itself (UNESCO/WHO/UNEP 1996).

Land use change impact on surface water

The main reason for land use change pattern is the fast development in socio-economic, which include change of cropland to urbanization, as well as changes within classes such as a change in crops or crop rotations. Particularly in regions where limited water is available, land use changes might result in an increment of water scarcity and thus contribute to a decline in living standards. This is mostly true in the case of the fast developing city like Pune in India. The major land use changes that were recognized were an increase in urbanization from 5.1 % to 10.1 % and agriculture from 9.7 % to 13.5 % of the catchment area during the 20 years. Urban growth was largely experienced in the eastern part and change to cropland in the mid-northern part of the catchment. Urbanization lead to rise of water yield by 7.6 %, and a related reduction of evapotranspiration, whereas the increase of agricultural area resulted in an increase of evapotranspiration by up to 5.9 %. (K. Schneider et al 2015)

Conclusion:

Hydrologic effect of land use change can be significant and have a variety of temporal and spatial results both positive and negative for humans. The demand of water increases as forecasted world- wide, including in those areas which are already experiencing high water-stress. Certain land use and land cover changes, some of which are happening at an increasing rate, and have distinctly negative impacts on water resources.

The impact of urbanization on groundwater has a major concern over past few decades, and in particular, for those involved in ground- water quantity and qualitative studies. Increment in impervious area due to urbanization results in decreased infiltration, and finally affecting the groundwater storage.

Existing literature demonstrated that progress has been made in identifying the potential consequences of various land changes and groundwater management, though there remains a clear need to improve the tools available to water resource planners to predict and manage the specific impacts of land change on Groundwater.

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